

Physician's Perspectives and Opinion towards the Utilization of A to Z Multivitamin Formulation – A Nationwide StudyGeethu George Thannikot¹, Amitrajit Pal², Dattatray Pawar³, Akhilesh Sharma⁴¹Department of Pharmacology, Shri. B.M. Patil Medical College and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka^{2,3,4}Medical Affairs Department, Alkem Laboratories Ltd., Mumbai

Received: 18-08-2024 / Revised: 21-09-2024 / Accepted: 26-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** A to Z multivitamin formulations, are widely prescribed to address nutritional deficiencies and support overall health across various patient populations. Despite their common use, data on physicians' perspectives regarding their clinical utilization is limited. This study aimed to explore prescribing patterns, perceived benefits, and physicians' attitudes and opinions toward A to Z multivitamin formulations.**Methods:** A nationwide, multicentre, cross-sectional study was conducted using a structured questionnaire. Physicians from specialties including paediatrics, general practice, and internal medicine were studied across multiple centres. The questionnaire assessed opinions, perceptions, and attitudes toward A to Z multivitamin formulations in both tablet and syrup forms.**Results:** In the interim analysis, responses from 6,095 healthcare professionals (HCPs) were included, with 3325 (54.5%) being general practitioners followed by 1459 (23.9%) paediatricians and 1313 (21.5%) physicians/ surgeons. The majority of 5554 (91.1%) HCPs regularly prescribed A to Z formulations most often due to nutritional deficiency 2947 (48.4%) and general well-being (45.9%). A significant number of 5406 (88.7%) of HCPs rated these formulations as highly effective, and 5640 (92.5%) reported no adverse events during usage. Additionally, 4695 (77%) considered them cost-effective compared to other multivitamins, and 5053 (82.9%) noted high patient compliance. Most of the HCPs, about 4695 (77%) also believed A to Z products play a definitive role in managing chronic diseases as well.**Conclusion:** The study provides valuable insights into the widespread acceptance of A to Z multivitamin formulations as effective, safe, and cost-effective options for various patient populations. These findings can inform future clinical recommendations and strategies for multivitamin supplementation.**Keywords:** Nutritional deficiencies, supplementation, multi-vitamin, multi-mineral.

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Introduction

Micronutrients (vitamins and minerals) are essential elements required by human and other organisms in varying amounts throughout life to support various physiological functions essential for maintaining health.¹ These multivitamins are available as dietary supplements and are best recommended by healthcare professionals (HCPs) when clinically necessary. Regular use of multivitamins can enhance nutritional status, especially in middle-aged and older adults; however, excessive intake may result in adverse effects. [1]

A broad selection of multivitamins is easily accessible in the Indian market, including both single-ingredient options and various combinations of vitamins, minerals, and other components. [2] Healthcare providers should consider each patient's

specific needs, medical history, and possible interactions with other medications or supplements before recommending these products. This approach aims to enhance the patient's well-being while reducing the risk of side effects.

The A to Z multivitamin formulation is commonly recommended by general practitioners, physicians, surgeons, and paediatricians. It includes a combination of both essential vitamins and minerals vital for improving overall health and well-being. People with inadequate nutrient intake from their diet, those on low-calorie diets, or individuals who avoid specific foods (such as strict vegetarians and vegans) may find a multivitamin formulation beneficial. [3] Additionally, A to Z multivitamin formulation is prescribed in order to address various issues like nutritional deficiencies

and malnutrition, which may vary significantly among healthcare facilities in India. There is a certain need to evaluate physicians' views and decision-making processes regarding multivitamin prescriptions. Such evaluations can help uncover the factors influencing prescribing behaviours and support efforts to promote the appropriate and consistent use of multivitamin supplements.

The primary aim of this cross-sectional study was to assess the opinions and perceptions of health care professionals across multiple specialties regarding A to Z multivitamin formulations for improving various health conditions thus reflecting its significance especially when adequate literature is deficient for the same and it becomes important to understand their perspectives to influence future clinical recommendations and strategies for multivitamin supplementation. It also seeks to identify any concerns or reservations that healthcare professionals may have about prescribing the A to Z multivitamin formulation for their patients.

Methods

A nationwide, multicenter, cross sectional, questionnaire-based study was conducted among qualified medical practitioners specifically general practitioners, physicians, surgeons, and pediatricians who were a part of this study. There was a total of 6095 HCPs from multiple centers geographically distributed all over India who responded to the study. A written approval was

obtained from the Ethics Committee prior to its conduction.

The study consisted of 15 structured multiple-choice questions which was pre-validated by experts to ensure its reliability and validity. The procedures were done according to the principles of the Good Clinical Practice (GCP), and the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) Guidelines.

The questionnaires were then administered electronically via a secure online platform, allowing for easy access and timely responses from participants. All responses were reviewed for completeness. Microsoft Excel was used for data analysis. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The data variables were expressed as numbers or percentages.

Results

The study was conducted among 6,095 healthcare professionals, predominantly consisting of general practitioners (54.5%), followed by pediatricians (23.9%) and physicians or surgeons (21.5%) as shown in figure 1.

The frequency of prescribing A to Z multivitamin formulations was examined and the results indicated that the majority of healthcare professionals (91.1%) regularly prescribe these formulations, reflecting a strong acceptance of this multivitamin formulation among various health care providers (figure 2).

Figure 1: Medical Specialty of HCPs

Figure 2: Frequency of prescribing A to Z formulations

Table 1: Conditions for prescribing A to Z Multivitamin formulations

Conditions for Prescribing A to Z Multivitamin Formulation	Numbers	Percentage (%)
Nutritional Deficiency	2947	48.4
General well-being	2793	45.9
Chronic disease management (Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension)	258	4.2
Pregnancy	88	1.4
Others	9	0.1

Majority of the HCPs prescribed A to Z multivitamin formulations due to nutritional deficiency (48.4%) and general well-being (45.9%). It was also advised for supporting chronic disease conditions' management (like in diabetes and hypertension) (4.2%) and in improving pregnancy outcomes (1.4%) as shown in table 1

and figure 3. The need for supplementation was assessed mainly through clinical evaluation (49.1%) and other factors like patient history (11.8%), and laboratory tests (3.7%). Many healthcare professionals (35.5%) considered all these factors collectively as illustrated in table 2 and figure 4.

Figure 3: Conditions for prescribing A to Z multivitamin formulations

Table 2: Methods to assess the need for A to Z multivitamin Formulation

Methods to assess need for A to Z multivitamin formulations	Numbers	Percentage (%)
Clinical evaluation	2991	49.1
Patient history	716	11.8
Laboratory tests	223	3.7
Combination of the three methods	2165	35.5

Figure 4: Various methods to assess the need for multivitamin supplementation

A notable 88.7% of healthcare professionals rated these formulations as highly effective (Figure 5), which explains their frequent prescription. The effectiveness was monitored mainly through clinical symptoms (49.6%) and other factors like laboratory tests (4.1%), and patient feedback (13.8%). 32% of healthcare professionals monitored using a combination of all these methods (table 3 and figure 6)

Figure 5: Effectiveness as rated by healthcare professionals

Table 3: Methods to monitor effectiveness of A to Z multivitamin formulations

Methods to monitor effectiveness of A to Z multivitamin formulations	Numbers	Percentage (%)
Clinical symptoms	3021	49.6
Patient feedback	839	13.8
Laboratory tests	253	4.1
Combination of the three methods	1982	32.5

Figure 6: Methods to monitor effectiveness of A to Z multivitamin formulations

The study underscored the safety of A to Z multivitamin formulations, with a significant value of 5640 (92.5%) of respondents not reporting any adverse events during use. Also, a substantial number of them did not experience any cases of

toxicity 5187 (85%). Furthermore, a notable value of healthcare professionals observed high patient compliance 5053 (82.9%), thus contributing to the frequent prescription of these multivitamins. (Figure 7)

Figure 7: Patient compliance of A to Z multivitamin formulations

Majority of the HCPs, 4695 (77%) believed that A to Z multivitamin formulations play a significant role in improving chronic disease conditions. Additionally, 4695 of HCPs (77%) viewed this formulation as cost-effective compared to other multivitamins.

Discussion

The primary reason people use multivitamin supplements is to enhance overall health and wellness and to address nutrient deficiencies in their diets. [4]

Our study is significant because it is a nationwide study that examines physician's views and perspectives on the use of A to Z multivitamin formulation in patients. It underscores the advantages of this formulations, including its effectiveness and patient compliance, which explains why it is commonly prescribed by healthcare professionals in clinical practice. A systematic review by Sarris J et al. found that multivitamin supplementation in both healthy individuals and those at risk primarily led to improvements in perceived stress, physical stamina, concentration, and overall mental health, along with significant reductions in anxiety and enhancements in self-reported vigor. [5] This suggests that multivitamin supplementation can enhance a person's overall well-being. Our study aligns with these findings, as physician's prescribed A to Z multivitamins for general well-being, in addition to addressing nutritional deficiencies, being the primary concern.

Dietary supplements are commonly taken during pregnancy to increase nutrient intakes, especially of key nutrients such as iron and folic acid. Some experts have hypothesized that multivitamin use might increase the chance of a healthy birth outcome. [6] In our study also, pregnant women did benefit from these multivitamin formulations.

Multivitamins play a vital role in maintaining physiological functions in the body. Individuals with diabetes often have lower levels of thiamine, pyridoxine, and biotin. While the exact reasons for this deficiency are unclear, supplementation has been associated with some improvements in metabolic control. Although metformin is the first-line treatment for type 2 diabetes mellitus, it can inhibit the absorption of certain nutrients, such as vitamin B9 and vitamin B12, making regular supplementation of these vitamins necessary for individuals with diabetes.

Additionally, those with low vitamin D levels are at a greater risk for diabetes and its complications, including cardiovascular disease. [7] Inflammation and oxidative stress are linked to both cardiovascular disease and cancer, and dietary supplements may provide anti-inflammatory and

antioxidant benefits. [4] Thus an improvement in these conditions are seen and it explains how A to Z formulations are helpful in supporting chronic disease conditions.

Multivitamin formulations can also be cost-effective and can thereby reduce the overall disease burden. For example, extended recovery after surgery (ERAS) protocols have shown significant benefits in multiple areas including early mobilization, improved pain control, and early oral intake, and the addition of multivitamin supplementation may enhance this process. [8] Our study responses show that most HCPs have found A to Z multivitamin formulations to be cost-effective, which can especially benefit the patients suffering from chronic disease conditions, where polypharmacy-related issues can hamper their economic well-being. It would certainly aid in the reduction of overall cost and disease burden and improve health outcomes eventually making it a valuable asset in supporting chronic disease conditions. A meta-analysis by Seoyoung Lee et al. suggests that multivitamin supplementation may positively impact free radical scavenging nutrient levels in plasma and enhance oxidative defense. [9] This aligns with our study, as many healthcare professionals indicated that the A to Z multivitamin formulations appear effective in addressing various health needs.

In a study conducted by Wong DH et al. to compare the compliance and efficacy of formulated vitamins versus individual vitamins, it was found that the group taking formulated vitamins showed better adherence to optimal dosages and higher compliance. [10] Our study similarly indicates that multivitamin formulations are of high patient compliance.

This along with cost-effectiveness make the supplement affordable to the patient especially in cases of chronic disease condition as they may require concomitant medications for a long duration of time. Thus, multivitamin formulations especially A to Z formulations, serve as an effective means to support nutritional health and thus general well-being of the patient.

Conclusion

Optimal nutrition is recognized for its positive impact on both mental and physical performance [1] and multivitamins, including A to Z multivitamin formulations, have the potential to improve health and prevent disease. They play a valuable role in addressing nutritional deficiencies, augment general well-being and improve pregnancy outcomes.

The study thus provides valuable insights into the widespread acceptance of A to Z multivitamin formulations as effective, safe, and cost-effective

options for various patient populations, particularly in paediatric and geriatric care. These findings can inform future clinical recommendations and strategies for multivitamin supplementation.

Acknowledgements

We extend our sincere gratitude to the healthcare professionals for their support in data collection, ensuring confidentiality and accuracy. We are thankful to Dr. Janarthanan and Dr. Aditi for their support. We are especially grateful to the patients whose medical information has greatly contributed to our understanding of the need and utilization of A to Z multivitamin formulation.

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